

The Influence of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture and Achievement Motivation on Teacher Performance Moderized By Commitment at Smkn 7 Surabaya

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ABSTRACT: Teacher performance is a crucial element in the world of education and is a determining factor in the level of quality of education, especially in formal environments such as schools, where student success is very dependent on the teaching and learning process led by the teacher. The quality of teacher performance has a significant impact on educational outcomes because they interact directly with students during the learning process. Therefore, more attention is given to developing quality teachers to support their performance. This research aims to analyze the influence of transformational leadership, organizational culture and achievement motivation on teacher performance, moderated by organizational commitment. The population in this research was 100 teachers who worked at SMKN 7 Surabaya as a permanent teacher. Then get 100 samples through a saturated sampling technique. Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Based on the analysis of 6 hypotheses, it was found that 5 hypotheses were accepted, and 1 hypothesis was rejected. The results of this research say that transformational leadership (X1) partially has a significant positive effect on teacher performance (Y). Organizational culture (X2) partially has a significant positive effect on teacher performance (Y). Achievement motivation (X3) partially has a significant positive effect on teacher performance (Y). The moderation of organizational commitment on the influence of transformational leadership and teacher performance produces a significant negative influence. Meanwhile, the moderation of organizational commitment on the influence of organizational culture and teacher performance produces an insignificant effect. Then the moderation of organizational commitment on the influence of achievement motivation and teacher performance produces a significant positive influence.

KEYWORDS: leadership, culture, motivation, commitment, performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Teacher performance is a crucial element in the world of education and is a determining factor in the level of quality of education, especially in formal environments such as schools, where student success is very dependent on the teaching and learning process led by the teacher. Teacher performance includes the implementation of educational tasks carried out by them as teachers. The quality of teacher performance has a significant impact on educational outcomes because they interact directly with students during the learning process. Therefore, more attention is given to developing quality teachers to support their performance. The educational paradigm is one aspect that provides policies in an educational institution. It also expands the resources and credibility of the institution and influences the formation of individual character and human resources within it. Education aims to improve the quality of individuals to be more productive and better. The success of an institution depends on the leadership within it, which is responsible for creating professional and independent human resources.

The problem in educational management that the author wants to examine is the impact of new leadership from the current change of principal at SMKN 7 Surabaya. Previously, of course, in the last 10 years there had been several changes in school principals. But the author will focus on the impact at this time, namely the role of leaders today. Can this new leadership pattern have a significant impact on the progress of SMKN 7 Surabaya. This research will focus on internal factors and factors that can influence teacher performance. On internal factors the author will focus on organizational commitment and achievement motivation. Meanwhile, external factors will focus on transformational leadership and organizational culture. In this research, organizational commitment will be used as a moderating variable, while transformational leadership, organizational culture and achievement motivation will be exogenous variables with teacher performance as an endogenous variable.

The impact of high organizational commitment includes improving teacher and school performance, low teacher turnover, creating a positive work atmosphere, and increasing job satisfaction for teachers and improving the quality of good education for

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schools, of course. Transformational leadership is a leadership style that focuses on inspiring and moving organizational members towards a greater common goal. Organizational culture refers to a set of values, norms, beliefs, and behaviors that are held and practiced by members of an organization. Achievement motivation refers to the internal drive that drives a person to achieve certain goals with high performance and good achievements. Therefore, this research was designed with the specific aim of investigating how transformational leadership, organizational culture, and achievement motivation, both individually and in combination, influence the formation of teacher performance as moderated by organizational commitment.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Ability, Motivation dan Opportunity Theory (AMO)

The Ability, Motivation, Opportunity (AMO) theory highlights three important components that influence employee character and organizational success: ability, motivation, and opportunity. This theory emerged from the interaction between the fields of industrial psychology, which emphasizes the importance of training and selection to improve performance (called ability), and social psychology, which highlights the role of motivation in performance (Cui & Yu, 2021).

B. Teacher Performance

Bintoro and Daryanto (2017: 105) say that performance is the willingness of a person or group of people to carry out activities or perfect them in accordance with their responsibilities with the results as expected. Teacher performance is the ability demonstrated by the teacher in carrying out his duties or work. Performance is said to be good and satisfactory if the goals achieved are in accordance with the standards that have been set (Darmadi, 2018: 34). Based on the description above, the author can conclude that teacher performance is their ability to carry out educational tasks according to established standards. Evaluation of teacher performance is carried out based on their level of success in guiding students towards educational goals effectively and efficiently.

C. Transformational Leadership

According to Stephen P. Robbin & Mary Coulter (2007: 194) transformational leadership is a type of leader who provides individual consideration, intellectual stimulation, and has charisma. Transformational leaders create profound change, both within themselves and their organizations. A transformational leadership style is a leader who is able to stimulate and inspire (transform) his followers to extraordinary things (Edison et al, 2017:98). Based on the understanding described above, the author can conclude that transformational leadership is a type of leadership that is able to inspire followers to believe in themselves and their potential in creating a better future for the organization. These leaders create profound change within themselves and their organizations, stimulating followers to achieve extraordinary things.

D. Organizational Culture

Robbins & Judge (2009: 296) Organizational culture refers to a system of shared meaning held by members that differentiates the organization from other organizations. Jerald Greenberg and Robert A. Baron (2003: 515) state that organizational culture is a cognitive framework consisting of attitudes, values, behavioral norms, and expectations that are mutually accepted by members of the organization. Based on the understanding described above, the author can conclude that organizational culture is a system of shared meaning held by members of an organization, distinguishing them from other organizations. This is a shared perception that forms a system that is interpreted equally by all members of the organization. Organizational culture is also a work activity that is influenced by social forces, and is a cognitive framework consisting of attitudes, values, behavioral norms and expectations that are mutually accepted by members of the organization.

E. Achievement Motivation

Achievement motivation can be said to be a motivation that aims to pursue achievement, namely to develop or demonstrate high abilities (Purwanto, 2014: 219). According to Susanto (2018: 35), achievement motivation is an individual's encouragement to do something as best as possible in order to achieve success. Based on the description above, the author can conclude that achievement motivation is the drive or desire possessed by individuals to achieve high achievement or success. This motivation encourages individuals to try to carry out activities as well as possible, develop their potential, and achieve established standards of perfection.

F. Organizational Commitment

Robbins and Judge (2013: 100) suggest that organizational commitment is defined as a situation where an employee sides with a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in that organization. According to Sutrisno (2018: 292), organizational commitment is; (1) a strong desire to become a member of a group, (2) a high willingness to work for the organization, (3) a certain belief and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization. Based on the description above, the author can conclude that organizational commitment is an employee's full support for the organization, including its goals and values. It reflects a desire to be part of a group, high effort to support the organization, and acceptance of the organization's values.

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This attitude also shows loyalty and a strong desire to stay in the organization and pays attention to the organization's continued success and progress.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

- H1: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Teacher Performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.
- H2: Organizational culture has a significant effect on teacher performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.
- H3: Achievement Motivation has a significant effect on Teacher Performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.
- H4: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.
- H5: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.
- H6: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Achievement Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMKN 7 Surabaya.

RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

The approach taken is quantitative research, which aims to verify the hypothesis that has been determined by the researcher. The research method applied in this study is a survey in the form of a questionnaire. This research used primary data which were retrieved from February to May 2024.

B. Population

The population in this study are subjects related to the research the author conducted at SMKN 7 Surabaya, so the respondents for this study were 100 teachers who worked at SMKN 7 Surabaya as permanent teachers. Then get a total of 100 teachers as samples using a saturated sampling technique. According to Kamaluddin (2021:74) Saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples. This is often done if the population is relatively small. A saturated sample is also called a census, where all members of the population are sampled.

C. Data Collection

The data source used in this research is primary data, namely information obtained directly from the original source. Primary data is information provided directly by the source to the person collecting the data (Sugiyono, 2017:193). Information for this study was taken from a questionnaire distributed to teachers at SMKN 7 Surabaya, with a focus on the influence of transformational leadership, organizational culture and achievement motivation on teacher performance and organizational commitment as moderation. After collecting and recording data, researchers carried out interaction analysis consisting of data reduction, data presentation and verification. The analysis of this research takes place along with the data collection process, or is carried out after the data has been collected.

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D. Data Analysis Method

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). PLS is a structural equation model (SEM) that is component or variance based. SEM is a field of statistical study that can test a series of relationships that are relatively difficult to measure simultaneously.

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether or not there is an influence between research variables. This test is done by analyzing the Regression Weight value, namely the Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values. The required limits are ≥ 1.96 for the CR value and ≤ 0.05 for the P value. If the data processing results show a value that meets these requirements, then the proposed research hypothesis can be accepted.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

Figure 2 Outer Model

To test convergent validity, Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are utilized. An indicator is considered to meet convergent validity in the good category if the Outer Loading > 0.7 and the Average Variance Extracted > 0.5 . The following are the Outer Loading and Average Variance Extracted for each indicator in this research variable:

Table 1. Convergent Validity Test - Outer Loading

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Transformational Leadership (X1)	X1.5	0.776
	X1.6	0.848
	X1.7	0.843
	X1.8	0.731
Organizational Culture (X2)	X2.3	0.744
	X2.4	0.793
	X2.5	0.828
	X2.6	0.782
Achievement Motivation (X3)	X3.1	0.756
	X3.2	0.802
	X3.3	0.798
	X3.4	0.827
	X3.5	0.732
Organizational Commitment (Z)	Z.1	0.738
	Z.2	0.843
	Z.3	0.775
	Z.4	0.726

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Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	
Teacher Performance (Y)	Z.5	0.794	
	Z.6	0.756	
	Y.3	0.758	
	Y.4	0.789	
	Y.6	0.774	
	Y.8	0.738	
	Y.9	0.762	
	Moderating X1*M	X1*M	0.977
	Moderating X2*M	X2*ZM	1.191
Moderating X3*M	X3*M	1.125	

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 1 Outer Loading above, showing that there are no indicator variables with outer loading values below 0.5, thus all indicators are considered suitable or valid for use in the study and can be used for further analysis.

Table 1. Convergent Validity Test - Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Transformational Leadership (X1)	0.642
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.620
Achievement Motivation (X3)	0.614
Organizational Commitment (Z)	0.598
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.584
Moderating X1*M	1.000
Moderating X2*M	1.000
Moderating X3*M	1.000

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 2, it is known that the Average Variance Extracted values for all variables in this study are > 0.5. Therefore, it can be stated that each variable has good convergent validity.

In the next section, the results of discriminant validity testing will be explained using Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values. An indicator is considered to meet discriminant validity standards if the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for the indicator on its variable are the highest compared to other variables. The following are the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values for each indicator:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity Test - Fornell-Larcker

	X1	X2	X3	M	Y	X1*M	X2*M	X3*M
Transformational Leadership (X1)	0.801							
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.611	0.787						
Achievement Motivation (X3)	0.416	0.603	0.784					
Organizational Commitment (M)	0.415	0.522	0.715	0.773				
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.472	0.569	0.652	0.665	0.764			
Moderating X1*M	0.377	0.285	0.127	0.343	0.191	1.000		
Moderating X2*M	0.234	0.150	-0.140	0.026	-0.023	0.756	1.000	
Moderating X3*M	0.111	-0.148	-0.257	-0.007	-0.080	0.645	0.649	1.000

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Test - Cross Loading

	X1	X2	X3	M	Y	X1*M	X2*M	X3*M
X1.5	0.776	0.556	0.394	0.406	0.416	0.302	0.180	0.029
X1.6	0.848	0.429	0.340	0.323	0.387	0.301	0.142	0.108
X1.7	0.843	0.528	0.347	0.311	0.409	0.271	0.176	0.064
X1.8	0.731	0.427	0.220	0.274	0.271	0.358	0.285	0.192
X2.3	0.584	0.744	0.436	0.371	0.315	0.237	0.139	-0.128

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	X1	X2	X3	M	Y	X1*M	X2*M	X3*M
X2.4	0.454	0.793	0.432	0.434	0.442	0.275	0.163	-0.033
X2.5	0.439	0.828	0.514	0.458	0.528	0.233	0.071	-0.146
X2.6	0.495	0.782	0.507	0.372	0.463	0.163	0.117	-0.158
X3.1	0.312	0.466	0.756	0.412	0.501	-0.017	-0.221	-0.335
X3.2	0.380	0.509	0.802	0.450	0.474	0.113	-0.030	-0.185
X3.3	0.370	0.490	0.798	0.614	0.464	0.147	-0.093	-0.162
X3.4	0.294	0.422	0.827	0.655	0.505	0.136	-0.108	-0.187
X3.5	0.284	0.471	0.732	0.644	0.584	0.118	-0.091	-0.140
M1	0.333	0.435	0.530	0.738	0.421	0.300	0.053	-0.003
M2	0.368	0.463	0.583	0.843	0.523	0.357	0.038	-0.058
M3	0.436	0.427	0.630	0.775	0.524	0.211	-0.025	-0.047
M4	0.318	0.413	0.581	0.726	0.556	0.173	-0.007	-0.051
M5	0.204	0.360	0.531	0.794	0.490	0.283	0.030	0.039
M6	0.263	0.327	0.455	0.756	0.544	0.278	0.038	0.089
Y3	0.374	0.518	0.510	0.598	0.758	0.155	-0.021	-0.116
Y4	0.401	0.454	0.498	0.467	0.789	0.142	-0.073	-0.048
Y6	0.297	0.437	0.598	0.547	0.774	0.199	0.015	-0.045
Y8	0.429	0.373	0.470	0.412	0.738	0.061	-0.010	-0.093
Y9	0.306	0.370	0.392	0.492	0.762	0.159	0.001	0.007
X1*M	0.377	0.285	0.127	0.343	0.191	1.000	0.756	0.645
X2*M	0.234	0.150	-0.140	0.026	-0.023	0.756	1.000	0.649
X3*M	0.111	-0.148	-0.257	-0.007	-0.080	0.645	0.649	1.000

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Tables 3 and 4, it can be observed that each indicator on the research variable has the highest Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values on the variable it forms compared to the Fornell-Larcker and Cross Loading values on other variables. Based on these results, it can be stated that the indicators used in this study have good discriminant validity in constructing their respective variables.

This section presents the results of reliability testing using composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha values. An indicator is considered to meet reliability standards if the composite reliability values are > 0.6 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998; Chin & Dibbern, 2010), and the rho_A and Cronbach's alpha values are > 0.7 (Vinzi, Trinchera, & Amato, 2010). The following are the values of composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha for each indicator:

Table 4. Reliability Test - Composite Reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Rho_A	Cronbach's Alpha
Transformational Leadership (X1)	0.877	0.828	0.815
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.867	0.814	0.798
Achievement Motivation (X3)	0.888	0.844	0.843
Organizational Commitment (M)	0.899	0.867	0.865
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.875	0.826	0.823
Moderating X1*M	1.000	1.000	1.000
Moderating X2*M	1.000	1.000	1.000
Moderating X3*M	1.000	1.000	1.000

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 5 above, it can be observed that the composite reliability values for all research variables are > 0.6, and the values for rho_A and Cronbach's alpha are > 0.7. These results indicate that each variable has met the criteria for composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha. Therefore, it can be concluded that the overall variables have a high level of reliability.

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B. Evaluation of Structural Model/ Inner Model

Figure 3 Inner Model

Based on the inner model scheme presented in Figure 3, it can be explained that the largest path coefficient is indicated by the influence of organizational commitment factors on teacher performance, that the coefficient equals to 10.313, followed by the influence of achievement motivation on teacher performance, equal to 5.678. Meanwhile, the smallest influence is shown by moderating X2*M on teacher performance, equals to 1.470. Based on these descriptions, it is evident that all variables in this model have positive path coefficients. This indicates that the larger the value of the path coefficient for an exogenous variable on an endogenous variable, the stronger its influence.

Table 5. R-Square

	R-Square
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.554

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in Table 6, it can be determined that the R-Square value for the teacher performance variable is 0.554, this indicates the ability of exogenous variables (transformational leadership, organizational culture, achievement motivation, and organizational commitment) to explain the endogenous variable (teacher performance) is 55.4% (moderate). The remaining 19.6% represents the influence of other unmeasured exogenous variables in this research.

Table 6. Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics ((O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Transformational Leadership (X1) → Teacher Performance (Y)	0.135	0.134	0.041	3.264	0.001	Significant positive
Organizational Culture (X2) → Teacher Performance (Y)	0.195	0.198	0.046	4.216	0.000	Significant positive
Achievement Motivation (X3) → Teacher Performance (Y)	0.246	0.245	0.043	5.678	0.000	Significant positive
Moderating X1*M → Teacher Performance (Y)	-0.102	-0.101	0.044	2.344	0.019	Significant negative
Moderating X2*M → Teacher Performance (Y)	-0.037	-0.037	0.025	1.470	0.142	Not significant

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signification
Moderating X3*M → Teacher Performance (Y)	0.083	0.083	0.030	2.714	0.007	Significant positive

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Table 7 shows the results of the PLS calculation which states the influence between variables. Based on the table above, it can be seen that of the 6 hypotheses processed in this research, it can be declared accepted or significant if the P-Values < 0.05 and T-statistics > 1.96. There is 1 hypothesis which states that the effect is not significant while 5 other hypotheses state that it has a significant effect. The following is an in-depth analysis regarding the influence between variables according to the proposed hypothesis:

H1: Transformational Leadership influences Teacher Performance

These results indicate that transformational leadership, as an approach that focuses on developing an inspirational vision, providing emotional and intellectual support to team members, and encouraging individual empowerment, appears to play an important role in establishing a work context that is conducive to improving teacher performance. In an educational context, this can be interpreted as a leader's ability to create an environment that allows teachers to feel connected to a common purpose, feel supported in their efforts, and be empowered to innovate and achieve higher standards of performance. Thus, these results provide strong evidence that transformational leadership practices have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance. The implication is the need to develop and strengthen transformational leadership in the educational context as a strategy to improve educational effectiveness and learning quality. Through this approach, schools can create a culture that supports innovation, creativity, and collaboration, which in turn can contribute to improving the overall quality of education. These results are in line with research conducted by Efendi, F (2023) and Fauzan, A., et al (2023), which said that transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on teacher performance. Meanwhile, these results are not in line with research conducted by Lustriningsih (2021) which states that transformational leadership style has a significant negative effect on teacher performance, then research by Aziz, N., et al (2022) and Insani, A.N (2020) which states that transformational leadership has an effect not significant to teacher performance.

H2: Organizational culture influences teacher performance

The research results show that organizational culture has a significant and positive influence on teacher performance. In this context, organizational culture includes the norms, values, attitudes and behavior that are accepted and practiced in the work environment of a school or educational institution. These findings suggest that factors such as clarity of vision and mission, mutual trust, collaboration, and support among staff members can influence how teachers interact with their work and achieve desired outcomes. Thus, these results highlight the importance of strengthening positive organizational culture in educational contexts. Through building a culture that promotes collaboration, open communication, recognition of achievement, and professional development, educational institutions can create an environment conducive to optimal growth and performance for teachers. This shows that investing in building a positive organizational culture can be an effective strategy for improving the quality of education and teacher welfare, as well as producing a positive impact on student learning. These results are in line with research conducted by Lustriningsih (2021), Efendi, F (2023) and Fauzan, A., et al (2023), who said that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Meanwhile, these results are not in line with research conducted by Dewi, R.L.P (2014), Mewahaini, H., et al (2022) and Tutu, R.V.B., et al (2022) which said that organizational culture has an insignificant effect on teacher performance.

H3: Achievement motivation influence on teacher performance

Research findings showing that achievement motivation has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance provide an illustration of the importance of internal factors in influencing professional performance. Achievement motivation, which includes the intrinsic drive to achieve high goals and strict standards, appears to be a powerful driving force behind the quality of teachers' work. When teachers feel driven by a desire to achieve excellence in teaching and student learning outcomes, they tend to experience increased commitment, creativity, and dedication in their work. Thus, these results suggest that paying greater attention to teachers' intrinsic motivation can be an effective strategy in improving their performance. It emphasizes the importance of creating a work environment that supports and strengthens intrinsic motivation, through empowerment, rewarding achievement, and creating opportunities for professional growth. In an educational context, strengthening teachers' achievement motivation can not only improve their performance, but can also have a positive impact on students' learning experiences and their academic outcomes. These results are in line with research conducted by Insani, A.N (2020), Fatah, A., et al (2021) and Aziz, N., et al (2022), who said that achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Meanwhile, these

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results are not in line with research conducted by Pragiwani, M., et al (2020), Lustriningsih (2021) and Hidayat Rahmat (2021) who said that achievement motivation has no significant effect on teacher performance.

H4: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Performance

Research findings showing that organizational commitment moderates the influence of transformational leadership on teacher performance with significant negative results provide an in-depth understanding of the complex dynamics in the interaction between organizational and leadership factors on individual performance. Although transformational leadership is often considered a factor that contributes positively to teacher performance, the results showing a significant negative impact when moderated by organizational commitment draw attention to the important role of individual commitment to the institution. Based on age distribution and education level, the majority of teachers are in the middle to old age category (43-52 years and > 52 years) and have a Bachelor's degree (S1). This context provides an understanding that these teachers have long work experience and a high educational background. These factors certainly play an important role in the significant negative impact of transformational leadership on teacher performance which is moderated by commitment. Older, more experienced teachers tend to have clear expectations regarding recognition of their experience and the values they have developed over the years. When the vision and initiatives of transformational leadership are not aligned with these values, conflict and stress can arise, potentially reducing their performance. Higher education also indicates that these teachers tend to be more critical of changes and innovations proposed by their leaders and tend to have higher expectations of the relevance and benefits of these initiatives. If expectations are not met or a leader's vision does not match the best practices they have mastered, this can negatively impact their performance. Overall, the distribution of teacher age and education provides an important context for understanding why transformational leadership does not always produce the expected positive impact on teacher performance, especially when moderated by high levels of commitment.

H5: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance

The research results showing that organizational commitment moderates the influence of organizational culture on teacher performance with insignificant results can be explained by considering the distribution of teachers based on age and most recent education. Older and more experienced teachers (aged 43-52 years and >52 years) tend to have high organizational commitment because they have worked at the school for a long time. This high level of commitment can reduce variability in their performance, making the influence of organizational culture insignificant when commitment is taken into account. Senior teachers who have long experience are usually familiar with the values and culture of the organization, so the influence of culture on their performance is not as big as the influence of their own commitment to the job and institution. Teachers with higher education (Bachelor's/Master's degrees) tend to have a deeper understanding of the importance of personal commitment to their work. They tend to rely more on personal commitment than organizational culture in determining their performance. Teachers with higher education often have good managerial skills and in-depth knowledge of their role, so they are better able to maintain high performance through personal commitment despite a less supportive organizational culture. This makes the effect of organizational culture insignificant because their performance is more influenced by strong personal commitment. Younger and less experienced teachers may be more influenced by organizational culture because they are still in the adjustment stage. A positive organizational culture can provide them with the guidance and support needed to improve performance. However, if organizational commitment is strong, the influence of organizational culture on their performance may also be insignificant. Because strong commitment can create a stable and productive work environment, reducing dependence on other factors such as organizational culture.

H6: Organizational Commitment moderates the influence of Achievement Motivation on Teacher Performance

Research findings showing that organizational commitment moderates the influence of achievement motivation on teacher performance with significant positive results provide a deep understanding of the complexity of the interaction between individual motivational factors and the work environment in influencing professional performance. These results indicate that when individual achievement motivation is supported by a high level of commitment to the institution, it can result in significant improvements in teacher performance. The interpretation of these findings indicates that organizational commitment can act as a moderating factor that strengthens the relationship between achievement motivation and teacher performance. When teachers feel emotionally connected and involved with the educational institutions where they work, their achievement motivation tends to be more focused and aimed at achieving organizational goals. This can encourage teachers to adopt a proactive and solution-oriented approach in facing challenges in teaching and learning. Thus, these findings highlight the importance of understanding the interactions between individual and organizational factors in improving teacher performance. This interpretation also emphasizes the importance of building an organizational culture that supports and strengthens individual commitment, as well as encouraging achievement motivation as a strategy to improve the quality of education and teacher welfare. By understanding these dynamics,

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educational institutions can develop a more holistic and sustainable approach to strengthening teacher motivation and performance, which in turn can have a positive impact on students' learning experiences and their academic outcomes.

V. CONCLUSION

The results show transformational leadership and positive organizational culture improve teacher performance through a supportive and collaborative environment. Achievement motivation also improves performance through commitment and creativity. However, organizational commitment negatively moderates the influence of transformational leadership, causing stress in teachers with high commitment, while not significantly moderating the influence of organizational culture. Organizational commitment strengthens the influence of achievement motivation, showing the importance of a supportive organizational culture.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. Further research is needed to explore additional factors that influence the interaction of the variables studied, enriching theories of motivation, leadership, and organizational culture in education. Collaboration with academics from various fields will broaden understanding and provide comprehensive insight into the complexity of the interactions of these variables.
2. To improve teacher performance, it is important to encourage transformational leadership and an inclusive organizational culture. Training for school leaders to understand organizational commitment and programs that stimulate achievement motivation through rewards, recognition and professional development is also needed.
3. To improve organizational culture and individual commitment in educational institutions, supporting policies are needed, leadership standards that strengthen organizational culture, as well as an evaluation system that considers achievement motivation and organizational commitment in assessing teacher performance.
4. Encouraging parent involvement in strengthening school culture and teacher commitment is critical. Support for teachers to create a conducive learning environment and open communication with schools regarding the contribution of parents in increasing teacher motivation and performance is also needed.

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